

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

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T1.3_Italian Lab 3rd Co-creation Workshop Report

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: *San Pietro Monumental Complex, Marsala (Trapani, Italy)*

EVENT DATE: *June, the 4th, 2024 (9-13:30 a.m. CEST)*

EVENT TITLE: *“Lo sviluppo consapevole dell’eolico offshore galleggiante: quali prospettive per la Sicilia?” / “A responsible development for the floating offshore wind technology: which perspectives for the Sicily Region?”*

TYPE OF EVENT: *Physical*

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: *Co-creation Workshop*

EVENT AFFILIATION: *EMD - European Maritime Day In My Country 2024*

LEAD ORGANISER: *APRE – Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (Agency for the Promotion of the European Research)*

CO-ORGANISERS: *University of York, RSE – Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico; RSE – Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (Research on the Energy System); the Institute of Marine Engineering (INM) of the CNR – Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (National Research Council)*

LANGUAGE: *Italian*

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The workshop has been organised as a follow-up of previous co-creation events hosted respectively by the Port Authority of Bari in June 2023 under the European Maritime Day initiative and the Port of Civitavecchia in March 2024. The third co-creation workshop, held in Marsala, deepened the state of the art of the deployment of FOWTs in the Sicily Region, investigating the specific opportunities and challenges, as well as the potential impacts generated in the area.

Starting from the presentation of MARINEWIND results up to date, the workshop offered a comprehensive overview of the maritime spatial planning and some offshore wind farm projects to be developed in the western area of the Sicily Region. The discussion focused on the possible co-existence and compatibility between offshore wind plants and other uses, especially fishing and navigation routes, and investigated the social acceptance of the new technology through an on-site questionnaire.

To this end, local fishermen and shipowners, local authorities and key industrial players in the green technology sector engaged in a direct debate, discussing on how to cooperate to favour the implementation of FOWT in the area.

OBJECTIVES

Inspired by the specific objectives of the MARINEWIND project, the workshop aimed at:

- Increasing awareness on FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.
- Encouraging social acceptance by directly involving local communities and local fishermen and by addressing any environmental issues.
- Facilitating communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and

indirectly involved in Italian MARINEWIND Lab.

TARGET AUDIENCE

Following the Quintuple Helix approach, the event targeted representatives of public authorities, civil society, green innovators, academia and industry directly involved in the Italian Lab. For each specific category, the involved actors were:

- **Industry:** FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, tech/project developers, trade associations (fisheries and tourism).
- **Academia:** Scientific & Research Community.
- **Public authorities:** at European (EC, European associations, e.g., ICLEI, ERRIN), national (Ministries for Energy, for Industry and Environment) and local level (Regional authorities), maritime transport authorities, policymakers.
- **Civil society:** NGOs, civil society organisations, and citizens.
- **Green innovation:** SMEs, public/private financial investors, insurers, ecologists, environmental organisations, and natural parks.

Additionally, through dissemination activities and synergies, the event targeted actors and beneficiaries of other EU funded projects and initiatives (e.g., the HE project FLOATFARM).

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: 33 participants

Figure 1 - Participants overview

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

2.1 Introductory session

The opening remarks of the third co-creation workshop include a speech delivered by Francesco Marchese on behalf of the Mayor of the City of Marsala, hosting the event, and followed by an intervention of Calogero Giuseppe Burgio, General Director of the Department of Energy, intervened on behalf of the Sicily Region.

Both intervention highlighted the peculiarities of FOWTs compared to onshore plants and other renewable energy sources, such as the need to be deeply rooted in the territory, adapting to its specific features and fostering its development. In fact, the installation of floating wind farms can generate benefits for the entire local community, with positive spill-over effects on employment, as well as the possibility of driving the development of a local supply chain. The benefits for the Sicily Region, where a huge number of projects are concentrated for a total of six billion euro, are multiple and linked to different areas. First, floating technologies foster the development of local ports, to be adapted according to the needs emerging in the operationalisation phase for the correct implementation of management activities. Secondly, the maintenance of the wind plants requires an extensive knowledge of the Mediterranean sea in which they are located, in order to reduce the potential dangers associated with the access to the platforms. For this reason, the use of specialised local workforce is essential, following ad hoc trainings targeting the local community. Finally, the Sicily Region has the opportunity and capacity to host the entire FOWT supply chain, which includes the engineering phase, the preliminary studies of the seabed and the marine currents, as well as the investigation of the effects for the local community. For these reasons, the strong connection of floating wind farms with the socio-economic fabric of the territory implies that all projects should be designed with a bottom-up approach, taking into account the impacts on the local community through an ongoing integration with all the actors potentially affected and fostering the involvement of young locals in all the deployment phases.

2.2 The MARINEWIND project: objectives and preliminary results

The first session of the co-creation workshop foresaw an introduction of the MARINEWIND project delivered by Paola Zerilli from the University of York as MARINEWIND scientific coordinator and leader of the specific Work Package dedicated to the analysis of financial solutions, techno-economic implications and commercialisation of FOWT. The intervention provided an overview of the preliminary results obtained within the first half of the project, focusing on the main financial barriers and enablers identified, followed by an introduction about the Contract for Difference (CfD) mechanism and the presentation of the Sicily Region case study.

Delving into the key financial barriers identified within the MARINEWIND project, the main criticalities are i) limited infrastructure and workforce specialised in offshore wind technologies leading to higher costs and delays; ii) need for significant investments in infrastructure and grid connections; iii) high financing and investment risks such as construction delays and market price uncertainties; iv) competition for resources in the coastal areas (e.g., tourism, fishing, and shipping interests); v) varied political and public acceptance based on perceived benefits, visual impact, and

economic considerations.

On the other hand, potential financial solutions to address the above-mentioned challenges and enable investments in the FOWT sector encompass i) **co-financing the development of ports** in central and southern Italy to support the offshore wind supply chain; ii) **Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs)** to extend the existing onshore wind incentives to offshore wind projects; iii) **R&D governmental and National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) funds** for projects linking research entities and industries to accelerate offshore wind development; iv) **governmental incentives and subsidies** (e.g., grants, tax credits) to make projects more attractive; v) **policy stability and long-term power purchase agreements (PPAs)** providing revenue certainty; vi) **risk mitigation instruments** (e.g., guarantees, insurance products, hedging mechanisms); vii) **green finance and sustainable investing** (e.g., green bonds and loans to access capital).

In this context, the Contracts for Difference (CfD) represent an innovative government funding source. A Contract for Difference (CfD) is a private law contract between a low carbon electricity generator and a government owned Low Carbon Contracts Company (LCCC). It incentivises long-term investments in renewable energy by providing developers with high upfront costs and revenue stability, protecting them from volatile wholesale prices and consumers from paying increased support costs due to the rise of the electricity prices. Renewable generator companies applying for a CfD are entering a private law contract with the government and being paid the difference between the *strike price* (set by the UK government, reflects the cost of investing in low-carbon technology) and the *reference price* (agreed market reference price) for the generated electricity over a 15-year period. Even though a specific target has been set in the FER2 Decree, with subsidies for up to 3.5 GW of floating offshore wind capacity to be reached by 2030, it is important to note that the date of auction, the strike price and the contract lifecycle have not been determined yet.

In the UK Lab, the CfD scheme is the UK government's primary mechanism for supporting low-carbon electricity generation. However, in that case, the CfD mechanism was not successful since the last auction went empty. Following this issue, the UK government proposed some adjustments, considering key financial variables, such as inflation, which have a long-term impact on the cost of the electricity.

Furthermore, the concrete benefits generated for the local communities should be considered as a pivotal criterion, beside the profit generated by the producers. To this end, the experiences of the Welsh and Scottish governments should be inspiring, since they have introduced a clause in contracts whereby part of the profit generated by the producers will be distributed within the local community, with benefits in terms of reduced energy costs. However, the benefits to the community also include ad hoc training sessions and seminars involving students with the aim to show them the potential of the wind farms and the career opportunities they could undertake, choosing a suitable faculty and pathway. In addition, the possibility of benefitting from tailored trainings creates new job opportunities to boost the local economy and labour market. In this way, the development of FOWTs generates earnings for citizens, stable electricity prices, and earnings for producers who could benefit from a stability throughout the duration of the contract.

Ongoing activities under the WP3 aim at performing a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis (CBA) for

FOWTs, focusing on estimating the Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE) and assessing the financial viability of wind farm projects, using data from the MARINEWIND Labs. Currently, the LCOE calculation is underway, involving the ratio of total project cost to total energy output. Key parameters under analysis include capital expenditures (CAPEX), operational expenditures (OPEX), capacity factor, weighted average cost of capital (WACC), and project lifetime. Accurate evaluation of the direct costs include the analysis and projection of development and consenting costs, turbine and platform costs, anchoring and mooring, installation, and cabling. Indirect costs, such as impacts on commercial fisheries and wildlife (birds and bats), are also being evaluated. In parallel, direct benefits such as revenues from electricity generation and the value of renewable energy credits are being quantified. Indirect benefits under consideration include broader societal and environmental gains, such as the social cost of carbon and improved air quality. Additionally, a sensitivity analysis is being conducted to estimate the LCOE under various scenarios. In this context, a preliminary work on the Sicilian wind farms is being realised, considering variables such as construction duration, regional multiplier, debt fraction, capacity factor, and overnight cost of capital.

Initial results suggest that the LCOE is highly sensitive to changes in capacity factor, WACC, and the number of wind turbines. For example, a two-year construction period yields an initial LCOE of €126.78/MWh, with the net present value (NPV) projected to turn positive by 2042. Extended construction periods are resulting in higher LCOE and delayed positive NPV outcomes. In parallel, the analysis considers macroeconomic impacts and financial risks associated with FOWT projects. Economic stability, market volatility, investment risks, and policy/regulatory changes are integral components of the CBA. Factors such as inflation rates, interest rates, and currency exchange rates are being analysed for their significant influence on the financial performance of FOWT projects. Market volatility in commodity prices (e.g., steel and copper) is also impacting overall project costs and financial planning.

Investment risks, including policy changes, technological advancements, and market competition, are being analysed to design robust financial models capable of withstanding uncertainties. Policy and regulatory changes are under scrutiny, with potential impacts on project viability from subsidies, tax incentives, and environmental regulations being particularly pertinent. By incorporating macroeconomic impacts and financial risks, the analysis aims to facilitate informed investment decisions, secure financing, and ensure long-term project sustainability.

2.3 The deployment and promotion of offshore wind technologies in Italy: challenges and opportunities

Challenges and opportunities linked to the deployment of FOWTs have been outlined in the intervention of Alessandro Monti, Assistant Professor at the University of Copenhagen. The presentation focused on the WINDMED - *Enhancing the Policy Framework for Offshore Wind Energy in the Mediterranean* project¹, funded by the Queen Mary's Centre at the University of Copenhagen. The WINDMED project, running from September 2023 until October 2024, has a three-fold aims: i) examine and address policy challenges for the development of offshore wind energy in the

¹ <https://jura.ku.dk/sustainabilityhub/windmed/>

Mediterranean; ii) propose policy interventions to facilitate the increase of offshore wind generation capacity; iii) facilitate the exchange of best practices between Denmark and other Mediterranean countries. To reach its objectives, the project has established a close cooperation with the Danish Embassy in Italy, securing a strong involvement of wind sector stakeholders and public authorities, whose contributions will be collected in a policy report to be presented at the end of the project.

Similarly to MARINEWIND, the WINDMED project analysed the main barriers affecting the deployment of FOWT in Italy, identifying the following challenges to be tackled:

- **Multiple and competing instances** resulting from economic, environmental and social considerations to be taken into account and adequately balanced in the definition of the objectives to be reached;
- **Enabling key factors to attract investors**, fostering the development of transparent policies and incentives to drive market growth;
- **Shortcomings linked to a predominant decentralised and “developer-led” approach**, in which the assignment of key areas to market operators is not guided by a central plan. Thus, the lack of comprehensive national Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) generates inefficiencies, failure to optimise the use of maritime space and potential overlapping amongst projects, as well as an insufficient implementation of Directive 2014/89/EU on maritime spatial planning.
- **Bureaucratic hurdles** in approval processes leading to obstacles and delays, as well as complications faced by developers in a later stage, despite receiving initial approvals.
- **Need for a shared vision amongst policymakers** on the role of offshore wind in the energy mix, fostering the dialogue between government, companies, and other stakeholders to enable collaboration and promote a sustainable development of FOWTs, while ensuring that offshore wind matches with the objectives of the energy transition.

On the other hand, the intervention highlighted the bunch of opportunities promoted by FOWTs for the Italian supply chain. First, the characteristics of FOWTs call for innovation, technological demands and cross-sectoral synergies, leveraging expertise from long-lasting economic activities (e.g., oil and gas), while acknowledging the need for advanced solutions. Secondly, FOWTs could foster the development of domestic manufacturing capabilities, creating a market for Italian producers (e.g., focusing on substations, cables, floaters), while enhancing the economic growth and job creation. Lastly, it drives investments in workforce training and technology transfer, which are pivotal factors to elevate domestic industrial capacity and competitiveness globally, while addressing the skills gap to foster innovation within the Italian offshore wind sector.

However, the following further actions need to be undertaken to accelerate the deployment of FOWTs in Italy and make the most from the above-mentioned opportunities:

- **Set up clear targets in terms of energy production** to foster investments in offshore wind plants in Italy. To date, according to the draft of the Italian NECP (2023), Italy aims to produce 2.1 GW from offshore wind plants by 2030, while the draft version of the FER2 Decree announces incentives for up to 3.8 GW offshore wind in auctions until 2028. The 2030 targets received a positive assessment from several market operators, considered it as good compromise between ambition and reality, in contrast with the criticism expressed by some

stakeholders, asking for reliable long-term targets for 2040 and beyond.

- **Invest in infrastructure development** including ports for the production, assembly, and delivery of floating platforms. This entails many challenges at different levels: i) logistical and administrative challenges to adapt port facilities to offshore wind operations; ii) ensuring that port yards have sufficient available space and are located near floaters' production facilities; iii) complex authorisation procedure requiring the coordination of several institutional actors including Port Authority for the update of harbour's plan, the Ministry of Environment for the approval of land and sea impact, the Ministry of Transport for the validation of the new function of the port, and port yard concessionaires. As starting point to tackle the above-mentioned challenges, the Energy Decree aims to identify two ports in Southern Italy and additional areas to be designated as offshore wind hubs.
- **Streamline the permitting procedure**, which is focused on the positive environmental impact assessment as essential requirement, by increasing its transparency to reduce the opacity perceived by market operators, limiting the relevance of many additional entities in the process (e.g. local authorities, cultural heritage agencies), and apply a stricter initial screening of viable projects to reduce the awaiting of approval.
- **Provide incentive schemes** to deal with higher costs, elevate investment risks and uncertainties in the Italian offshore wind market and risk due to the lack of experience with floating technologies, while enabling a major predictability of revenues and bankability of projects. Pivotal aspects for incentives include the importance of non-price criteria like product quality and local content and the suggestion to adjust incentives to inflation and price fluctuation of materials.
- **Consider environmental protection aspects** including a preliminary assessment of the visual impact, geotechnical analysis and archaeological studies, considering that the preservation of archaeological assets is a key concern in the Italian context. Thus, integrated planning strategies to balance biodiversity protection while fostering renewable energy development should be developed, ensuring the effective management of the impacts generated by both onshore and offshore project.
- **Foster social acceptance amongst the local communities** to facilitate the sustainable development of offshore wind projects and their alignment with socio-economic instances and political concerns. Thus, in order to enhance the social acceptance, the project planning should set up a comprehensive communication strategy to educate and address misconceptions, foster stakeholders engagement, and establish an open dialogue aimed at showing how the society could benefit from FOWTs deployment (e.g., advantages of renewables over fossil fuels; impact on employment). Moreover, obtaining a social license to operate helps to reduce and mitigate financial risks.

As previously mentioned, the WINDMED project serves as a facilitator for the cooperation between Italy and Denmark in the offshore wind energy, promoting knowledge exchange with a forerunner country and upscale the deployment of FOWTs starting from Denmark's wind farm planning and marine area protection valuable insights. Moreover, the project focuses the EU policy context linked to the deployment of offshore wind energy through the analysis of key initiatives (e.g., REPowerEU, EU Wind Energy Package, Net-Zero Industry Act, EU Critical Raw Materials Act), which contribute to i) simplify the procedures and encourage investment in wind energy infrastructure through reforms of

the electricity market; ii) minimise risks in resource extraction, manufacturing, and waste management building supply chain transparency and sustainability; iii) introduction of trade barriers impacting the raw material sourcing from outside the EU; iv) balance protection of domestic industries with essential material supply through the diversification of the supply chains and investment in domestic production.

2.4 FOWT social acceptance: the first-hand experience of Renexia

Mauro Fabris, vice-president of the National Association of Wind Energy (ANEV) and institutional relation officer for Renexia, shared a first-hand experience from the industry and based on the planning of the fixed wind farm to be built from October 2024 in Maryland, presented as a good practice to be potentially replicated in Italy for the deployment of offshore wind farms. In the Mediterranean area, Renexia is responsible for the design of the Med Wind project², which is located 80 kilometres from Trapani and 40 kilometres from the Egadi Islands. The project envisages a plant of almost 3 GW and will mobilise an investment of 9 billion euro, in addition to the 25 billion already committed to conduct studies and preparatory campaigns.

Following the experience in the United States, Renexia acknowledges the need to foresee specific actions to engage the local communities living in the areas where the wind plant projects are located, starting from the very initial planning phases. Fostering dialogue and open discussions with neighbouring territories and key actors, including the local community, the fishing industry and trade unions, is a pivotal action to increase the social acceptance and take the project forward by demonstrating that offshore is concrete, sustainable, and can co-exist with different instances and realities. Furthermore, the dialogue with the local community should be conducted on the basis of a sound scientific knowledge of the objectives to be achieved and its spill-over effects on the locals. Thus, Renexia invested in a series of preliminary studies, which included environmental and geotechnical analysis, oceanographic and archaeological campaigns mapping a surface of 800 km² and leading to the identification of two relics from the Second World War in the area of interest.

In the model promoted by Renexia, the above-mentioned preliminary studies are complemented by the creation of a continuous dialogue with all the social partners involved, enabling the establishment of a functional mutual understanding for the realisation of the project in a sustainable way, bringing together the different demands and specific needs of all the actors involved.

Furthermore, it is crucial to develop lasting agreements and relationships with the territory at multiple levels. Firstly, with the industrial supply chain, which includes technicians, local authorities and trade associations, to ensure long-term maintenance and prevent plants from being abandoned, as happened in the case of photovoltaic plants. Secondly, it is important to enter into ecological sustainability agreements with national and international environmental associations. In the case of Renexia, before obtaining the signature and support of six major environmental associations, four awareness-raising campaigns to prove the sustainability of FOWTs were needed. Thirdly, it is crucial to ensure sustainability from the social perspective, with a primary focus on the spill-over effects on

² <https://renexia.it/med-wind-progetti/>

employment and organising meetings at regional level to better define the expectations of the local community.

2.5 The Maritime Spatial Planning: the case of the Sicily Region

MARINEWIND project partner RSE – Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (Energy System Research) gave an overview of the current situation for the authorisation process and the Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) in Italy, deepening on the current situation of the Sicily Region. All data presented have been released from the Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security and is updated as of April 30, 2024.

In total, 21 requests for permission have been presented around the Sicily Region area, with the scoping phase that has been concluded for 14 projects, while only one project has already received a positive Environmental Impact Assessment. The majority of the projects (13 out of 22) applied a wind turbine called *Vestas V236*, with a capacity of 15 MW, a rotor diameter of 236 meters and a hub height of approximately 150 meters.

RSE collected the current offshore wind farm projects located in different areas of the Sicily Region, which has been analysed according to three key dimensions (bathymetry, producibility and distance from the coast), as follows:

- **12 projects in the Strait of Sicily**, located in areas with *fishing, environmental protection and natural resources*, and *maritime safety, navigation and surveillance* as priority sea uses and beyond 12 nautical miles from the coast (territorial waters limit), with a seabed depth of less than 500 meters and a producibility greater than 3500 MWh/MW (calculated at 150 meters above sea level). The projects are partly overlapping.
- **2 projects in the area of Agrigento and Gela**, with a project located in areas with *fishing and maritime transport and ports* as priority sea uses and within 12 nautical miles from the coast, with a seabed depth of less than 500 meters and a producibility between 2500 and 3500 MWh/MW. The second project is located in a zone with *environmental protection and natural resources, maritime transport and ports* and *maritime safety, navigation and surveillance* as priority sea uses and beyond 12 nautical miles from the coast (territorial waters limit) in areas with seabed depths between 60 and 1000 m and producibility between 2500 and 3500 MWh/MW.
- **2 projects in the perimeter of the Pelagie Islands**, located in an area with *environmental protection and natural resources* and *maritime safety, navigation and surveillance* as priority sea uses and beyond 12 nautical miles from the coast with seabed depths between 500 m and 1000 m and producibility exceeding 3500 MWh/MW.
- **1 project in the western Ionian sea (city of Catania)**, located in an area with *generic use* and *maritime transport and port* as priority sea uses and beyond 12 nautical miles from the coast, with a seabed depth of more than 1000 m and producibility between 2500 and 3500 MWh/MW.
- **5 projects in the around Malta**: 3 projects located in areas with *environmental protection and natural resources, maritime transport and ports* and *maritime safety, navigation and surveillance* as priority sea uses; 1 project in an area with generic use and 1 project outside

the MSP. All projects are located beyond 12 nautical miles from the coast.

Specific area	N. of projects	Seabed depth	Producibility	Distance from the coast
Strait of Sicily	12	< 500 m	>3500 MWh/MW	Beyond 12 miles
Agrigento and Gela	2	< 500 m 60 – 1000 m	2500 – 3500 MWh/MW	1 project beyond and 1 project within 12 miles
Pelagie Island	2	500 – 1000 m	>3500 MWh/MW	Beyond 12 miles
Western Ionian sea	1	< 1000 m	2500 – 3500 MWh/MW	Beyond 12 miles
Malta	5	< 500 m	2500 – 3500 MWh/MW	Beyond 12 miles (2 projects not included in the mapped area)

Table 1 Offshore wind farm projects located in the Sicily Region

Furthermore, the intervention provided an overview of the current state-of-the-art of the regulatory framework related to the deployment of FOWTs. It is important to underline that the Italian Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP), required by the European Directive 2014/89 to be delivered by 2021, is available only as a draft resealed in August 2022 and is currently under the Strategic Environmental Assessment procedure and, consequently, not yet adopted.

However, the authorisation procedures for offshore wind plants and further guidance on the identification of suitable areas in the Italian landscape have been defined in the **Art. 23 of the Legislative Decree 199/2021** (transposition of the European Directive 2018/2001 RED II on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources). More in details, the decree states that:

- the authorisation can be issued by the Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security (MASE) in agreement with the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport (MIT), following a consultation with the Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry (MASAF) for the offshore plants and with a single procedure including the issue of the concession for the use of the maritime state property (amendment of the Art. 12 of the Legislative Decree n. 387, 29 December 2003).
- The areas identified as suitable for the installation of offshore wind plants are the ones reported in the maritime space management plan.
- In the suitable areas for the installation of wind plants, the competent authority regarding the landscape shall issue a non-binding mandatory opinion identifying, if needed, specific prescriptions to eventually protect archaeological areas of interest and fostering the harmonisation within the landscape.

Lastly, Italy set additional measures to foster the development of the supply chain related to floating offshore wind plants included in the Legislative Decree “Energy Security” (Art.8, Law n.181, 9 December 2023) stating that, within 30 days, the MASE will publish a call to collect expressions of interest for the identification of maritime state-owned areas for the offshore floating wind power supply chain located in at least two ports in Southern Italy or in port

bordering areas where the use of coal is being phased out. Moreover, the MASE adopted and published a vademecum on the fulfilments and information necessary to start the single procedure for the authorisation of floating wind plants, in a context in which the National integrated plan for Energy and Climate 2023 revised the offshore wind target of 2.1 GW by 2030.

2.6 Off-shore wind farm projects and marine spatial planning: focus on the Sicily Region

Considering that the third co-creation workshop related to the Italian Lab was specifically focused on the Sicily Region, this session aimed at presenting one of the several offshore wind farm projects in this area.

Giorgio Di Liddo intervened on behalf of ENI Plenitude to present the 7SEASmed project³, which will be composed by 21 turbines of 12 MW each (for a total of 252 MW), to be located in an area with a seabed depth ranging from 130 - 350 metres and more than 35 kilometres from the coast, covering an area of about 50km². As a result of a process started in early 2022 and followed by preliminary geotechnical and geophysical investigations, the 7SEASmed project was the first project to obtain a positive Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) granted by the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security in the first quarter of 2024. The entry into operation of the 7SEASmed plant is foreseen between 2028 and 2029, preceded by a Contract for Difference (CfD) auction in 2025 (waiting for the FER2 Decree), and the financial close and assignment of supply contracts in 2026.

Initially, the portfolio of offshore wind plant projects has been developed by two Italian companies, namely NiceTechnology and 7SeasWindPower, with the support of two key investors (Copenhagen Infrastructure Partners and GreenIT) which will acquire the 100% of the projects share before the construction phase, while the development phase is financed entirely from the majority shareholders' own funds. The portfolio includes a total of five projects characterised by common features such as i) wind turbines with an horizontal-axis and a specific power comprised between 12 and 17 MW; ii) wind turbine composed by a three-blade rotor with a diameter of up to 260 m mounted on a tower at an elevation of approximately 150 m above the sea level; iii) floating foundations made of steel; iv) the electrical energy produced is transported by submarine power lines and then fed into the grid at TERNA's delivery stations.

Di Liddo underlined the strategic importance for each company to have a portfolio of projects located in the same area due to the length of the authorisation procedure and the lack of a centralised approach in the identification and assignment of suitable areas. However, he noted that the deployment of offshore wind projects in all the stages, from the development phase up to the financial closing, are capital intensive compared to other type of technologies. As an example, development costs for the 7SEASmed and IchnusaWindPower projects are estimated to amount to approximately EUR 130M in total. Main higher costs are resulting from marine and environmental studies (e.g., sediment sampling for geotechnical analysis, oceanographic campaigns, preventive archaeology campaigns), design of floating foundation and dynamic cables for site-specific conditions, and the preparation of authorisations documents (e.g., Environmental Impact Study).

³ <https://www.7seasmed.it/>

Moving from the general context to the specific case of the 7SEASmed project, preliminary environmental studies and preventive archaeological campaigns have been conducted, showing that the identified surface does not correspond with any protected area and does not overlap with any primary fishing zone.

As already mentioned in the previous interventions, the collaboration with the local community is crucial in order to maximise the social acceptance of the offshore wind plants. To do so, the 7SEASmed project involved the local community from the very beginning of the planning phase, collecting their opinions and major concerns to be concretely addressed. In particular, the visual impact has been indicated as main cause of the opposition to the implementation of such projects. However, the presentation showed that the offshore wind technologies are characterised by a lower visual impact due to the distance of the plants from the coast.

Furthermore, Di Liddo outlined the main spill-over effects arising from the installation and operationalisation of the 7SEASmed wind plant and affecting the city of Marsala and, more widely, the Sicily Region and its inhabitants. The key benefits could be summarised as follows:

- **Implementation of compensation actions** funded by the 7SeasMed project, such as the intervention on tourist (e.g., Tuna factory in Favignana) oriented towards the renewal of the area and with a potential boosting effect on tourism.
- **Fostering the production of green energy** equal to about 4.4% of Sicily's needs and 646,000 households.
- **Spill-over effects on the national and local economy** since the deployment of FOWTs can potentially involve key sectors such as construction materials, metalware, advanced mechanics, ships and vessels and electrical equipment, in which Italy has a leading role in the European context. Moreover, FOWTs drive value creation through investments in the national supply chain and port infrastructures (e.g., boosting a market for high-tech boats and local ports) which can activate an economic flywheel in economic and employment terms. As already mentioned, ports are of pivotal importance for the offshore wind industry, since they are needed throughout the complete life cycle of the plant, including minor ports dedicated to assembly and integration and for installation and operation phases. In Italy, the Ministry for the Environment and the Energy Security launched a call for expressions of interest to identify suitable areas and ports for the deployment of FOWTs. Regarding Sicily, the Port of Augusta applied.
- **Spill-over effects on the labour market** in terms of job creation, with the employment of approximately 700 people in the construction phase and 40 people during the operationalisation phase, as well as in the whole supply chain. As an example, data shows that each installed GW can generate more than 1,300 new jobs and an economic value on the territory (between direct indirect and induced effects) of about €2.9 billion⁴. Moreover, the deployment of FOWTs call for the need of reskilling the local workforce through ad hoc trainings in order to educate high-qualified professionals with the partnership of the local

⁴ <https://www.ambrosetti.eu/le-nostre-community/floating-offshore-wind-community/>

industries (e.g., professional training course in partnership with the University of Palermo in 2023/2024, registering the attendance of more than 25 students).

2.7 The impact of FOWTs on local economic activities: the perspective of fishermen's associations

The co-creation workshop encouraged the active participation of fishermen's associations in order to listen to their opinions on the topic, as well as collecting their specific instances that need to be carefully considered to ensure a sustainable deployment of FOWTs, in line with the needs of

The interventions of the fishermen's associations invited as speakers discussed the challenges and opportunities related to the possible co-existence between the offshore wind farms and the other uses of the sea, especially fishing.

The first intervention was held by Giovanni Basciano, Regional Manager for Sicilian fisheries at the General Association of Italian Cooperatives (AGCI), who reflected on the reasons why the fisheries sector is opposed to the European trend to transfer the generation of green energy in the sea. The instances advanced by fishermen are directly linked to the key challenges currently affecting the fishing sector. Over the past few years, fishery decreased by the 35% the quantities of the fish caught and by 20% its value, with the resulting reduction of the employment rate by 20%. In addition, the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) is financing a partial withdrawal of trawling and longline as fishing techniques.

- **Increasing restrictive regulations** imposed both by European authorities and local NGOs, as well as by the need to co-exist with other uses of the sea, which are limiting the available area to be reserved to fishing. In fact, the general perception expressed by the fishermen's associations is that the regulations defined at the European level are massively promoting the deployment of offshore wind technologies and green energies in general, while disregarding the specific demands of the fisheries at local level, ignoring the co-existence with other uses of the sea and further limiting the fishing areas. During the intervention, key data about the fishing sector in Italy have been presented, showing how it is subject to major restrictions compared to the rest of Europe. Limitations include: i) the obligation to local fishing within 6 miles; ii) inshore fishing within 20 miles; iii) dealing with pre-defined quotas; iv) the longline technique applicable only up to 55 km and further limited by the wind farms, due to the 50 km drifting.
- **Fishing no longer considered as an attractive job** by the young people. Despite of the fact that fishery was a key sector in the Sicilian local economy, covering the whole area around the Sicily region and involving more than 2,000 fishing boats operating along the region's coastline, representing approximately 1/5 of the national fleet, it has not developed as much as other sectors, such as tourism. As already mentioned, the most penalised professions are longliner and trawl fishing since the use of Italian seas for trawling is 32%.
- **Spill-over effects generated by the crisis of the fishing activities on the entire supply chain** and related economic sectors, including ship building, fish processing in which the Sicily Region plays a leading role, and the potential negative effects of tourism, which is a driving

sector for the local economy.

To ensure compatibility between the fishing sector and the development of offshore wind farms, it is essential to study and have a deep understanding of the impact generated at the local level, to be reached through an open dialogue with all the actors potentially involved. In fact, a shared planning of the wind farms, taking into account the specific demands of fishermen and the geotechnical characteristics of the Mediterranean and its seabed, as well as the restrictive regulations in force that hinder fishing activity in Italy and differ significantly compared to the rest of Europe, should be promoted throughout the whole process. Fostering this kind of holistic approach could generate mutual benefits for both fishery and FOWTs deployment, introducing a more adequate regulatory framework to leverage on the sea as renewable resource, respecting the timing of reproduction of the fauna and strengthening fishery as a key sector for the local economy.

The second intervention on behalf of the local fishermen was held by Marco Tramati as representative of the fishermen's association linked to the tuna fishing in Marsala, who highlighted the pivotal role of the Marsala navy as an important reference point in the national landscape, due to the constant assistance provided to other ports and the advanced fishing system developed over the years. Moreover, the Port of Marsala is specialised on the fishing of tuna and swordfish, which is considered as a crucial economic activity for the entire Sicily Region, providing employment for a large majority of the local population.

When it comes to the development of offshore wind farms, in the past, fishermen have expressed negative opinions, despite the possibility to have clean energy at low cost. In order to gain fishermen's full support to the deployment of FOWTs, it is crucial to ensure that specific demands and needs are taken into account from the initial planning stages. Fishing, in fact, is an economic activity that is severely restricted by current regulations limiting the quotas of fish that can be caught. For this reason, collaboration with the fishing sector is a prerequisite for the development of wind farms. This would allow a better use of the sea's renewable resource, with wind power promoting the repopulation of protected areas while respecting biological spawning times, as well as studies of the seabed that could also be used to understand the spawning grounds of a certain type of fish. On the other hand, it is crucial to replace restrictive fishing measures with good regulation and management practices. Moreover, boats, thanks to current advanced systems, do not represent potential damage to areas where floating turbines are present. In conclusion, fishing and wind farms are compatible realities.

Following the interaction with the experts intervened during the co-creation workshop and the presentation of several opportunities for both the co-existence with the other uses of the sea and for positive impacts on the economic activities and the community, local fishermen and shipowners showed a concrete interest in cooperating with public authorities and industrial stakeholders to favour the implementation of FOWT in the territory, recognising the MARINEWIND project as their elective channel to protect the fishery sector through specific recommendations at the EU level.

3 ROUNDTABLE TOPICS OVERVIEW

Following the presentations delivered by the experts, the roundtable discussion was foreseen as a

closing session of the co-creation workshop, opening the floor to participants to share their points of view, suggestions and concerns regarding the deployment of FOWTs. During the debate, which included also questions from the participants to the speakers after each intervention, the following criticalities, barriers and possible solutions emerged:

- According to the industry representative, the Italian industry does not have the capacity to address market demands in a short time, in terms of provision of all the necessary components (e.g. turbines, cables). In fact, according to the latest estimate, cables built in Italy could be available only starting from 2029, while the target set at both the European and national level are referring to 2030. Moreover, available sites and resources to leverage on for the development of the FOWTs supply chain, such as the ILVA located in Taranto, do not have adequate capacity for the needed steel production. Thus, a revision of the timeframe to reach the targets set could be needed, rather than externalise the whole process.
- Fishermen's associations asked for more details regarding the cables. ENI Plenitude confirmed that, in the case of the realisation of the 7SEASmed project, the onshore infrastructure will be invisible and the export cables will be buried a couple of meters below the seabed. The route of the cable towards the mainland will be realised through a controlled horizontal drilling technique and will return to the surface of the seabed at approximately 500-600 metres from the coast. Then, the cable will continue its path towards the area of Partanna still buried under the roadway and passing through the industrial zone of Marsala. Thus, the only inconvenience will be caused by the worksite for burying the cable. However, it was recognised that the placement of the anchoring with respect to the foundation could represent a potential problem for the navigation routes.
- To this input, the fishermen's associations replied that, in reality, the trawling technique does not interfere with the wind plants located around the Marsala coast, due to the new technologies applied. Moreover, they highlighted that the longline could be retrieved without damaging the installations.
- Although the deployment of FOWTs could potentially being in conflict with other uses of the sea, it is possible to find solutions to ensure the co-existence, especially through the application of advanced technology which could be beneficial also for fishermen. For instance, facilities could be useful to create forecasting models for currents, following the example of what happens with weather. Furthermore, understanding the advanced demands and specific needs of the local fisheries sector is crucial to ensure multi-level coordination and to find practical and functional solutions.
- The industry further emphasised the importance of organising formal roundtables at national level to further discuss the guidelines and next steps, as well as the need to involve trade associations and local stakeholders, including local navies and fishermen, throughout the phases of the project design and operationalisation. The ongoing dialogue with the social players is pivotal to enable a sustainable development of the wind plants, according to the peculiarities of the geographical and socio-economic context in which the project is located. As an example, the issues to be addressed by ENI Plenitude for the realisation of the 7SEASmed project were significantly different from the ongoing discussions undertaken for the projects located in the Sardinia Region.

- Regarding the dialogue with local associations and fishermen, the industry highlighted that it should not be oriented only towards the investigation of possible compensation systems, but it should focus on potential solutions to facilitate the co-existence among FOWTs, other uses of the sea and local economy, especially the instances coming from the fishery sector. This aspect should be taken into account when choosing the specific technology to be installed in order to ensure a sustainable deployment of FOWTs while safeguarding the fishing sector and avoiding its further decline.
- During the roundtable, industry reflected on the role played by Italy in the development of FOWTs. Even though the FER2 legislative decree foresees support measures dedicated to energy operators and the Ministry for the Environment and the Energy Security has launched a call for expressions of interest to identify two ports for the deployment of FOWTs, the above-mentioned measures are only guiding action that has yet to be translated into opportunities and financial support for the creation of suitable areas, adequate infrastructure and incentives targeting industrial operators. At this stage, it is crucial to finance companies and industrial operators to be provided with the needed instruments to realise a technological upgrade of key sectors for the deployment of FOWTs. For instance, the Italian metalwork sector has great capacity to be further exploited. However, to date, is located inland and is oriented towards other types of production, so it could not be converted to the production of components for the wind industry in the short term.
- The potential of the Italian construction industry has been underlined also by Renexia, especially with regards to ship building sector. More broadly, in order to secure a leading role of European industry in the FOWT sector and fully exploit the opportunities provided by the internal available resources, a change of mindset is needed. More in details, the State should be aware of development potential inherent in the sector and then take action to boost the construction capacities at an industrial level, considering that most of the companies are state-controlled. Furthermore, the above-mentioned actions should be implemented in a short time to guarantee the achievement of the objectives defined by the National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan and the European Commission.
- To this input, it was underlined the need to provide funding at the national level in order to adapt the production system and the available technologies to the wind energy industry, leveraging on the high-quality skills, workforce and resources that are currently available within the European Union. Thus, the technological upgrade of industry should be supported by regulatory measures and financial incentives in order to secure Europe's leading role in the wind energy industry and keeping the production in-house. Key investments should be realised in robotics and automation as enablers for a new industrial production systems, allowing Europe to gain a strategic position in the international market and successfully reaching the targets set for energy production.
- The need for major investments in key sectors for the deployment of FOWTs and ad hoc initiatives to support large industrial players, rather than focusing mainly on the investments related to ports infrastructure, should be discussed at the European level. The discussion should be fostered also considering that many countries outside the European Union recorded an increasing competitiveness due to the possibility of access to state aid, which could potentially hinder Europe's growth in the wind energy sector. Moreover, the lack of

support measures in Europe is causing the lengthening of the timeframe, which no longer matches with the urgent market needs.

- In order to successfully address the market needs, changes in finance is needed. Envisioned solution foreseen include i) subsidised rates for companies investing in renewables, generating a positive impact on the environment; ii) green prize to be considered as part of the return on investment; iii) changes in the public procurement rules which with the introduction of criteria considering the environmental and economic impact on business, the level of innovation of the technologies applied and the profitability of the investment. However, it was highlighted once again the importance of establishing synergies among the social partners involved at local, national and European level, the finance sector and the local and national authorities.

4 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

The MENTIMETER survey to be administered to the audience of the third Italian co-creation workshop held in Marsala was slightly changed compared to the previous events. Taking into consideration the foreseen a major participation of civil society, local fishermen and environmental organisations, specific questions were added, aiming at collecting the opinion of the local community on the deployment of FOWTs. Thus, the questions asked to the audience during the interactive session were oriented towards the investigation of FOWTs impacts on three pivotal aspects, namely i) local economic activities; ii) environment; iii) benefits to the local community, in line with the MARINEWIND objectives. The results collected will be used as a baseline to measure the increasement of social acceptance of FOWTs throughout the duration of the project.

In total, 14 attendees actively participated in the MENTIMETER survey. The first question aimed at investigating the background of the respondents, showing that the majority of the audience came from research centres (57%) and industry (29%), followed by universities (7%) and authorities (7%).

Regarding the impact of floating offshore wind farms could have on local economic activities, such as fishing and tourism, most of the participants considers it as moderately positive (38%) and positive (31%), with only one respondent (8%) assessing a strongly positive impact from the economic perspective. On the other hand, 15% of the respondents indicated a neutral impact generated by FOWTs on the local economy, while one participant (8%) expressed a moderately negative opinion.

Che tipo d'impatto pensi che i parchi eolici offshore galleggianti possano avere sulle attività economiche locali (e.g., pesca, turismo)?

Figure 2 Impact of offshore wind farms on local economic activities

When assessing the kind of impact of floating offshore wind farms could have on the environment (e.g., biodiversity), the audience identified itself with two opposite opinions. According to the 36% of the respondents, FOWTs have a positive impact on the environment, while the 29% expressed a moderately negative perspective, adding a 7% who assessed it as negative. It is worth to mention that the 21% of the respondents agreed on a neutral effect of FOWTs from the environmental perspective.

Figure 3 Impact of the offshore wind farms on the environment

Regarding the potential benefits that floating offshore wind farms could bring to the local community in terms of employment, energy savings, better air quality, and general improvement of quality of life, all the respondents identified a positive impact generated by FOWTs, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 4 Impact of offshore wind farm on the local community

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The third co-creation workshop organised within the Italian Lab has been dedicated to keep collecting barriers perceived by the stakeholders for the sustainable deployment of FOWTs, with a special focus on fishermen’s associations and the perspectives for the Sicily Region, while reflecting on enablers and potential solutions, including how to enhance the social acceptance and drive investments in the offshore wind sectors. The barriers and enablers identified were connected with the possible solutions emerged throughout the workshop, as summarised in the table below.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS & SOLUTIONS	
Lack of a comprehensive national Maritime Spatial Planning replaced by a “developer-led” and decentralised approach for and the assignment of areas to market operators.	Optimise the project location balancing the distance from the coast, bathymetry conditions, the specific geographical features if the Italian waters and the wind resource availability.	Need to synchronise the regional objectives developed with a bottom-up approach.
	Fostering a common vision amongst policymakers on the role of offshore wind in the energy mix, ensuring that the deployment of FOWTs matches with the objectives set for the energy transition	Foster a political planning to optimise the use of maritime space and avoid potential overlaps and conflicts among projects.

<p>Bureaucratic hurdles in the approval process causing significant delays and complications in later development stages, despite initial approvals.</p>	<p>Streamline the permitting procedure by increasing its transparency to reduce the opacity perceived by market operators, decreasing the indirect relevance of numerous additional entities, applying a stricter initial screening of viable projects to reduce the awaiting of approval.</p>	<p>Developing a portfolio with more than one wind farms project located in the same area to tackle the long awaiting time of approval and the lack of a centralised identification and assignment of suitable areas.</p>
<p>Lack of a comprehensive and predictable regulatory framework resulting in uncertainties and obstacle to full-scale commitment from international market players.</p>	<p>Market attractiveness characterised by a strong industrial demand and a good wind potential (e.g., over 130 proposed projects from Italian and foreign operators).</p>	
<p>Logistical and administrative challenges related to the adaptation of port facilities to offshore wind operations.</p>	<p>Invest in the development of ports and infrastructure for the production, assembly, and delivery of floating platforms. The Italian Energy Decree aims to identify two ports in Southern Italy and areas to be designated as offshore wind hubs.</p>	
<p>Complex procedure requiring the coordination among multiple institutional actors (e.g., Port Authority, Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Transport, port yard concessionaires) to approve the assignment of new functions to the port.</p>		
<p>Lack of capacity of the Italian industry to address market demands in a short time, in terms of provision of all the necessary components (e.g. turbines, cables), which could be available only starting from 2029.</p>	<p>Set up clear, achievable and reliable long-term targets achievable in terms of energy production to foster investments in offshore wind plants in Italy.</p>	<p>Provide financial incentives and state aid to foster the adaptation of the Italian industry to the offshore wind needs, leveraging on the available skills and capacities of key sectors.</p>
<p>Numerous technological challenges, such as hurdles to achieve technological readiness and regarding floaters assembly and design, dynamic cables, floating sub-stations.</p>	<p>Promote the knowledge exchange with forerunner countries in the FOWTs sector leveraging on the insights provided by operating wind farms (e.g., partnership between Denmark and Italy established by the WINDMED project).</p>	

		Build an European supply chain to maximise local value creation and address safety and reliability concerns (e.g., Chinese manufacturers offering potentially suitable turbine designs).	Invest in workforce training and technology transfer to elevate domestic industrial capacity and competitiveness globally and address the skill gap to foster innovation within the Italian offshore wind sector.
The deployment of the wind plants is capital intensive compared to other type of technologies, due to the need to carry out preliminary marine and environmental studies, geotechnical analysis and preventive archaeological campaigns; design floating foundation and dynamic cables for site-specific conditions; prepare authorisations documents.		Ensure the bankability of projects as a key driver for the uptake of FOWTs and in a competitive market.	Provide incentive schemes to address high costs, investment risks and uncertainties in the Italian offshore wind market, enabling a major predictability of revenues and bankability of projects.
		Financial enablers include feed-in Tariffs; Innovation and R&D fundings; government incentives and subsidies; policy stability and long-term contracts; risk mitigation instruments; green finance and sustainable investing.	
FOWTs characterised by a lower level of technology readiness and lack of track-record compared to onshore wind.	The Italian context regarding energy mix relies historically on fossil fuels, especially gas.	Reduce path dependency from fossil fuels to foster the establishment and market uptake of emerging renewable energy technologies.	
Lack of social acceptance amongst the local communities and key actors, including environmental and fishermen's associations, due to widespread misconceptions, lack of proper and timely information on the implementation of the projects, lack of awareness regarding the potential benefits generated by the wind farms.		Implementation of compensation actions oriented towards the renewal of the area and with a potential boosting effect on tourism (e.g., Tuna factory in Favignana funded by the 7SEASmed project).	
		Foster the production of green energy to address the local consumption and guarantee stable and reduced electricity price.	

		Spill-over effects on the local economy and labour market in terms of job creation, reskilling opportunities and ad hoc trainings.	Engage with the local community and stakeholders throughout all the phases of the project through awareness-raising campaigns, seminars, educational activities, roundtables to collect in advance their concerns and expectations while increase the social acceptance.
The fishing sector is facing a major crisis, with a 35% decrease in the quantities of the fish caught and a 20% reduction of the employment rate, affecting the whole supply chain. FOWTs could further boost the negative effects of the crisis.		Consider the specific demands and needs expressed by fishermen from the initial planning stages to gain their full support to the deployment of FOWTs.	Allow a better use of the sea as renewable resource, with wind power promoting the repopulation of protected areas while respecting biological spawning times, as well as studies of the seabed that could also be used to understand the spawning grounds of a certain type of fish.
The Italian fishery is severely affected by restrictive regulations imposed both at the EU and local level, which are limiting the available area to be reserved to fishing activities.	The trawling technique is the most affected by the strict regulation on the use of the sea, with only a 32% of the entire surface available.	New technologies applied to trawling are consistent with the offshore wind farms.	Replace restrictive fishing measures with good regulation and management practices.
The visual impact of FOWTs is regarded by the civil society as one of the major concern and ground for opposition to FOWTs deployment.		Studies and simulations show that the visual impact of wind farms is almost invisible due to the distance of the plants from the coast.	

	<p>Preservation of archaeological assets is a key concern in the Italian context.</p>	<p>Drafting of an integrated planning strategy considering environmental protection aspects, the assessment of the visual impact and the preservation of archaeological assets, balancing biodiversity protection while fostering FOWTs development.</p>
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